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THE USE OF ERP SYSTEMS IN EUROPE

It grew on average by 9.7% between 2016 and 2021 for the countries considered

Desi index calculates the value of Electronic Information Sharing, or the number of companies that have used an ERP-Enterprise Resource Plannig software package to share information between different functional areas such as accounting, planning, production, and marketing.

Data are available for 2016-2021 for DESI countries that exclude UK from the dataset.

Ranking of countries by value of Electronic Information Sharing in 2021. Belgium is in first place by value of the percentage of companies that use ERP-type models with a value of 8.77%, followed by Denmark with a value of 8, 2% and from Lithuania with an amount equal to 8.0%. In the middle of the table there are Italy with a value equal to 5.89%, Cyprus with a value equal to 5.55% and Slovenia with an amount equal to 5.4%. Romania closes the ranking with a value of 3.91%, followed by Bulgaria with an amount of 3.89% and Hungary for an amount of 2.38%.

Ranking of countries by percentage change in Electronic Information Sharing between 2016 and 2021. Latvia ranks first in terms of the percentage change in Electronic Information Sharing between 2016 and 2021 with a value equal to 103.38% to an amount of 2.73 units. Poland is in second place with an amount equal to 36.85% equal to an amount of 1.28 units, followed by the Czech Republic with an amount of 25.63% equal to an amount of 1.29 units. In the middle of the table there are the Netherlands with an amount of change equal to an amount of 6.21% equal to an amount of 0.46 units, followed by Belgium with an amount equal to 5.15% equal to an amount of 0.43 units, and from Greece with a value equal to 4.93% equal to an amount of 0.30 units. Hungary closes the ranking with an amount equal to -10.52% equal to a variation of -0.28 units, Sweden with an amount of -12.69% equal to an amount of -0.91 units, and Cyprus with a value of -22.10% equal to an amount of -1.58 units. Overall, the value of the use of Electronic Information Services between 2016 and 2021 grew by an average of 9.73% for the countries considered.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is then carried out. The analysis shows the presence of two different clusters composed as follows, namely:

- Cluster 1: Greece, Sweden, Italy, Cyprus, Belgium, Spain, Finland, Luxembourg, France, the Netherlands, Lithuania, Denmark, Portugal, Austria;
- Cluster 2: Estonia, Poland, Ireland, Bulgaria, Croatia, Germany, Latvia, Malta, Romania, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, Czech Republic.

From the point of view of the median value of the clusters it is clear that the value of Cluster 1 is equal to an amount of 7.17 while the value of cluster 2 is equal to an amount of 4.76. It follows that the countries of cluster 1 are characterized by the presence of a much higher number of companies that use ERP-type management tools for company management.

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Network Analysis using the Manhattan distance. Network analysis is then applied using the Manhattan distance. The data show the presence of two complex network structures. There is a complex network structure between Portugal, Austria, Luxembourg and Finland. In particular, the following relationships are present:

- Finland has a link with Luxembourg with a value of 0.39 units;
- Luxembourg has a link with Austria for a value of 0.32 and with Finland for an amount of 0.39;
- Austria has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount equal to 0.32 and with Portugal equal to an amount of 0.31 units.
- Portugal has a connection with Austria with an amount of 0.31 units.

There is a complex network structure between Poland, Estonia, Ireland, Germany, Croatia, Malta, Slovakia, and Slovenia. In particular, the following connections are detected:

- Poland has a connection with Estonia for an amount equal to 0.32 units;
- Estonia has a connection with Ireland for an amount of 0.35 units and with Poland for an amount of 0.32 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Estonia for an amount equal to 0.35 units and with Germany for an amount equal to 0.30;
- Germany has a connection with Croatia for an amount equal to 0.45 units, with Malta for a value equal to 0.30 units, and with Slovakia for an amount equal to 0.4 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Germany for an amount equal to 0.45 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Germany for an amount equal to 0.4 units, with Malta for an amount equal to 0.26 units and with Slovenia for an amount equal to 0.32 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Slovakia with a value of 0.32 units and with Malta for an amount of 0.38 units.

Conclusions. In summary, it should be noted that the use of ERP systems has certainly increased in the various DESI countries. However, there are still significant differences between European countries as demonstrated by the cluster analysis. It should also be emphasized that probably due to the state of current technologies and the corporate culture of SMEs, it is not correct to consider the use of ERP systems with reference to all companies. It would be more correct to consider only medium to large enterprises. In fact, ERP models are more easily applicable in medium-large companies where the issue of the efficiency of management systems is more present. Small and medium-sized enterprises may have problems implementing ERP-type models due to both software management costs and a lack of corporate culture.

Declarations

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